

Transition towards environment friendly consumer products by co-creation of an oxidoreductase foundry

GA no 101000607

Research and Innovation Action (RIA)

Start date: 1st June 2021. End date: 31st May 2025

Public Executive Summary of deliverable D5.4

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101000607

Disclaimer: This publication reflects only the author's view, and the Research Executive Agency is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

Executive summary log

Submission	30-01-2025
Lead beneficiary-organisation	NORCE
Responsible person	Gro Bjerga
Name and affiliation contributing persons	Rasmus Ree, Øivind Larsen, Yuleima Diaz (NORCE); Irina Chiriac (LEITAT)
Name and affiliation internal reviewers	Andrew Ellis (BIOCATS), Damien Demoulin (CALYXIA), Aroa Rey Campa (LEITAT)

Main achievements/outcomes

This Deliverable D5.4 concludes main work on one of OXIPRO's four innovation pillars, the nutraceutical case. The objective in the OXIPRO nutraceutical case and the proof of application (POA) experiment is to use an enzyme system to remediate the odorous trimethylamine from fish protein hydrolysates to reach a satisfactory score in consumer perception.

Over a million tons of fish byproducts are produced by Norwegian fish farming and aquaculture annually (Myhre *et al*, 2024). Of these byproducts, 88% are used today, but largely for non-human markets such as bioenergy and feed. Fish protein hydrolysates (FPH) are nutritious and represent a way to use byproduct proteins as food. Food-grade FPH is produced using proteolytic enzymes, which digest proteins into small water-soluble peptides. Following enzymatic proteolysis, peptides are isolated from non-protein fractions, concentrated, and dried, resulting in a highly nutritious protein end product. In total, 1000 tons of food-grade FPH was produced in Norway in 2023 (Myhre *et al*, 2024). This FPH could be used as ingredients in nutraceuticals, but implementing hydrolyzed fish proteins in food products may be hindered due to their distinctly fishy odor, and in practice little to none of this FPH goes to human consumption (Myhre *et al*, 2024). The fishy odor is caused by volatile molecules (Hebard *et al*, 1982; Steinsholm *et al*, 2020); a well-known contributor is trimethylamine (TMA) (Leonardos *et al*, 1969; Hebard *et al*, 1982).

The report shows how a thermostable monooxygenase can be used to remove trimethylamine (TMA) in FPH (Goris *et al*, 2020; Goris *et al*, 2023). For these experiments, FPH was produced from fish by-

products using a conventional approach, and enzymes were produced by and used in downstream processing of the FPH. The final product were studied by chemical analysis which allows monitoring the conversion of TMA to investigate if the target molecule is depleted from the sample after treatment. In addition, the product was analysed by sensory studies to find out how the organoleptic perception of the hydrolysate is after treatment. The results are currently being prepared for publication and are therefore not disclosed in this public summary.

References

Goris M, Cea-Rama I, Puntervoll P, Ree R, Almendral D, Sanz-Aparicio J, Ferrer M & Bjerga GEK (2023) Increased Thermostability of an Engineered Flavin-Containing Monooxygenase to Remediate Trimethylamine in Fish Protein Hydrolysates. *Appl Environ Microbiol*: e00390-23

Goris M, Puntervoll P, Rojo D, Claussen J, Larsen Ø, Garcia-Moyano A, Almendral D, Barbas C, Ferrer M & Bjerga GEK (2020) Use of Flavin-Containing Monooxygenases for Conversion of Trimethylamine in Salmon Protein Hydrolysates. *Appl Environ Microbiol* 86: e02105-20

Hebard C, Flick G & Martin R (1982) Occurrence and significance of trimethylamine oxide and its derivatives in fish and shellfish. In *Chemistry and biochemistry of marine food products*, Martin R (ed) pp 149–304. Westport, CT: AVI Publishing Group

Leonardos G, Kendall D, Barnard N, Leonardos G, Kendall D, Barnard N, Threshold O, Leonardos G & Barnard N (1969) Odor Threshold Determinations of 53 Odorant Chemicals Odor Threshold Determinations Of 53 Odorant Chemicals. 2470

Myhre M, Richardsen R, Nystøyl R & Strandheim G (2024) Analyse marint restråstoff 2023 SINTEF Ocean AS

Steinsholm S, Oterhals Å, Underhaug J, Måge I, Malmendal A & Aspevik T (2020) Sensory Assessment of Fish and Chicken Protein Hydrolysates. Evaluation of NMR Metabolomics Profiling as a New Prediction Tool. *J Agric Food Chem* 68: 3881–3890